

Critical Making

D1.2 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

About this document

Date	30.6.2021
Dissemination level	Public
Responsible Partner	ZSI
Work package	WP 1 Project Management
Editor	Barbara Kieslinger (ZSI)
Authors	Barbara Kieslinger (ZSI), Klaus Schuch (ZSI)
Reviewers	Katja Mayer (ZSI)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101006285.

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Contributor	Comments
v1	26.4.2021	Barbara Kieslinger Klaus Schuch	First structure and outline Input regarding data management infrastructure at the coordinator's site
v2	31.5.2021 - 14.6.2021	Maria Åkerman, Caroline Christiansen, Lisa M. Seebacher, Regina Sipos, Melanie Stilz, Victoria Wenzelmann	Input regarding data collection for each WP
v3	18.6.2021	Kaja Meyer	Peer Review
v4	30.6.2021	Barbara Kieslinger	Final editing

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Executive summary	6
Introduction	7
Data Summary	9
FAIR Data	11
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	11
2.2. Making data openly accessible	13
2.3. Making data interoperable	17
2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	17
3. Allocation of resources	18
4. Data security	19
5. Ethical aspects	20
6. Summary and outlook	21
7. References	22

Critical Making

LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Confidential
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
EGE	The European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIG	Global Innovation Gathering e.V., Germany
GIM	Grassroots Innovation Movements
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
R&I	Research & Innovation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
STEM	Science Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics

TUB Technische Universität Berlin, Germany

VTT Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus VTT OY, Finland

WIF Wikifactory Europe SL, Spain

WP Work Package

WP1 Project Management

WP2 Building the critical making knowledgebase: concept & methods

WP3 Case Action: GENDER

WP4 Case Action: YOUNG TALENTS

WP5 Case Action: OPENNESS

WP6 Evaluation, Impact, Future Implications

WP7 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

ZSI Zentrum für Soziale Innovation, Austria

Executive summary

Critical Making aims to add scientific insights into the potentials of the maker movement for critical, socially responsible making, and show how these communities can offer new opportunities for young makers of all genders to contribute to an open society via open innovation. It is a collaborative research project with partners from 4 European countries and connected to a global community of innovation hubs, makerspaces, hackerspaces and other grassroots innovation community spaces, initiatives and individual innovators, makers, technologists and changemakers.

Responsible data management is crucial for any research project and the Data Management Plan (DMP) provides structured guidelines for this process. The DMP covers the lifecycle of data, including the process of collection to storage, analysis and preservation. In this DMP we provide a basic description of what kind of data will be produced and collected during the course of Critical Making, and details about what will happen to the data both during this project and after it has been completed.

Critical Making is part of a pilot action on open access to research data and is thus committed to providing access not only to project results and processes, but also to data collected during that process. Although the general policy of the Critical Making project is to apply “open by default” to its research data, we have to handle privacy issues with special care. Legal rules on anonymity are highly relevant and need to be agreed upon with each of the participants. Most of the data in Critical Making will be anonymised data, but in case of a doubt, the data privacy of our participants always prevails over open data policy. When dealing with personal data Critical Making is making sure that all GDPR rules are followed, including e.g. data minimisation, which states that data has to be adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary for the purposes for which they are processed.

Overall, the leading framework for our data management is the GDPR in terms of personal data protection, FAIR data for the handling of non-personal research data and Open Access following the European Union's Open Science Guidelines¹².

Introduction

A Data Management Plan (DMP) is a key element of most research projects that collect or handle original data. This DMP describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by the Critical Making project, following the Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020 provided by the European Commission³. As part of making research data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR), a DMP should include information on:

- the handling of research data during and after the end of the project
- what data will be collected, processed and/or generated
- which methodology and standards will be applied
- whether data will be shared/made open access and
- how data will be curated and preserved (including after the end of the project).

This document provides a first version of the DMP and includes all the information we have available at this point in time. As stated in the guidelines, *the DMP is intended to be a living document in which information can be made available on a finer level of granularity through updates as the implementation of the project progresses and when significant changes occur*. Therefore, we implement this deliverable as a document that can be updated by the partner

¹https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en

² <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/legislation-open-data>

³https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

organisations at any time in the course of the project. In preparation for the mid-term review we will also reflect on the status of the DMP with the whole consortium and address any possible needs for updating the document and the processes described in it.

As RRI is in the nature of our project, Critical Making is committed to the integrative concept of **Responsible Research and Innovation**, which clearly goes beyond a pure ethical aspect. A key maxim in a RRI process is not only to have researchers but all societal actors work together to align the research process and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of European society. The importance of the approach is to align this process in a reflective way that is a transparent, interactive process by which societal actors and innovators become mutually responsive to each other. Allowing an appropriate view to RRI the project will develop several activities around a reflective RRI process for all its stakeholders, summarized within the project handbook. Aim of the RRI aspects in the handbook is to raise the awareness of the RRI concept and its implication for the day-to-day work in the project and acting accordingly. In practice this adapted RRI approach will be put in place by an open and reflective session on RRI in all face2face project meetings.

By involving different stakeholders in the case actions our research activities may touch on sensitive ethical issues, respectively the protection of (possibly) sensitive private data. The Project Handbook (D1.1 published in Month 3) and this document describe in detail how Critical Making actors intend to collaborate when conducting the case action studies and handle privacy and security issues. All work packages will look specifically into all ethical and legal issues related to the data they are dealing with and a responsible Data Protection Officer (DPO) has been assigned. Project partners are aware of these sensitive issues and will build on ongoing European work on the management of trust and a code of conduct.

1. Data Summary

What kind of data is handled by this project and what is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project? In the following we list the main characteristics that describe research data and that we have applied to describe our Critical Making research data in Table 1 (at the end of this document).

Type of data

Following the Data Management Plan of the Time4CS project (Time4CS Consortium, 2021), the following type of data may be collected and documented in research projects:

- **Observational:** data captured through observation of an activity and/or a behaviour in real-time (and, therefore, usually irreplaceable). The collection usually may require human observation, surveys and instruments to record the information.
- **Experimental:** data obtained in controlled situations through the active intervention of researchers, who design an activity (called experiment) to collect data. They can be reproduced if needed, but it may be expensive.
- **Simulation:** data generated reproducing a real-world system, usually used to determine what would happen in certain conditions.
- **Derived or Compiled:** data derived upon transformation of existing data sets to create new data. They can be reproduced if lost, but it is very time-consuming and it could be expensive.
- **Reference or Canonical:** it refers to data used to categorize and/or classify other data. They could be static or changing over time.
- **Event-related:** data collected during events. As they are real-time events, they are irreplaceable. They can include personal data of participants, and GDPR will be applied.

While most of the research data can be assigned to one of these categories in some cases there could also be an overlap. Some data can belong to more than one category depending on the specificities of the data itself (e.g. event-related data could also be considered observational data upon certain conditions).

Re-use of existing data and origin of data

Next to the collection of genuinely new data sets research work can also rely on existing data and generate new collections out of existing data sources. The re-use of existing data sources should thus also be identified as well as the origin of the data to be used in the research process.

Format of the data and estimated size

Research data can have various formats: text, numeric, multimedia, models, software languages, discipline and instrument specific, etc. It is important to describe the format of the data in order to facilitate its accessibility and interoperability. Thus, preference should be given to open and standard formats. Likewise, data management experts advise to give indications about the size of the data collected in a DMP. Similar to the format of the data size is relevant for future data sharing and making data accessible. In the course of the time this information should be revised and updated accordingly.

Aim of the data and the process of data collection

Part of the data description should always be the aim of the data produced and how it is linked to the objectives of the project. Similar, a short description of the process of the data collection that will be applied helps to characterise the specific data.

In Table 1 at the end of this document we describe the Critical Making data in as much detail as we can at this stage of the project. We try to consider all the points mentioned above and update Table 1 in case of additional data being handled in any of our research activities.

2. FAIR Data

FAIR data means that the data is **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable, and **R**e-usable. In this section we elaborate on the measures the project is taking to generate FAIR data during the course of the project and for its use beyond that timeframe.

2.1. MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

Versioning

The data sets produced in Critical Making will follow good research practice by following a set of naming and versioning conventions, which is very useful for collaborative projects. A version control system will be applied to make sure that the data is organized, and we can track back different versions of the datasets. Such a version control system, which is also sometimes referred to as revision control system, tracks incremental versions (or revisions) of files over time. Nextcloud, which is the main collaboration and data sharing system running on a ZSI server, supports a simple version control system for files. Through this version control system, the risk of losing information after modifications in a collaborative process where many partners are working with the data is minimized.

In addition to this automatic versioning via the collaborative system we are also applying version numbers in the file name itself (see naming convention below).

Naming

For the naming of our shareable data we will use file names that are informative and useful for both humans and machines in order to make the data accessible and findable. Names should be meaningful, on the one hand, in order to make it easy for others to understand what the file contains and how it should be used. On the other hand, it should use deliberate delimits in order to be machine readable. A common approach is using “_” and “-” to

delimit units of metadata in the file names. For this project we suggest using "-" to separate words you want to glob together and "_" to separate different information within a file name. What we should avoid are blank spaces, punctuation, capital letters or special characters (e.g. characters such as \$, @, %, #, &*, (,), !, etc. may have meanings in programming languages).

As mentioned above the naming should also always include a version number to make sure others who want to make use of any data set knows that they are dealing with which version. An example of an appropriate for a data file is:

CriticalMaking_OnlineRoleModels_Collection_Codes_v1.xml

Keywords and metadata

Descriptive and substantive (i.e. how the data should be read or interpreted) metadata will be elaborated and described in a readme.txt file complementing each dataset (see Table 1). This detailed documentation should help interested users to clearly understand and reuse the data.

Table1: Metadata description

Creator(s)	Main person(s) involved in producing the data
Title	Name or title by which the dataset is known.
Contributor(s)	Person(s) or organization(s) responsible for making contributions to the dataset.
Publisher	Holder of the data (e.g. in archives), person or institution who submitted the work.
Data ownership	Indication of primary data controller (person) and indication of additional data ownership, especially in the case of shared ownership;
Year of publication	The year when the data was or will be made publicly available.
Data created	The date when the resource itself was put together; this could be a date range or a single date.

Description	Concise description of the contents of the dataset. Describe the research objective, type of research, method of data collection, type of data and storage location of data (especially in the case of data not available on Zenodo).
Subject	Subject, or key phrase describing the resource.
Temporal coverage	Indicate the dates to which the data refer. Enter the year or beginning and ending dates.
Spatial coverage	Describe the geographic area to which the data refer (e.g. municipality, town/city, region, country). The geographic coordinates of the area may be included, if desired.
Identifier	Zenodo automatically assigns a DOI to a dataset once the entire deposit procedure has been completed. In some cases, a dataset may be known by one or more (persistent) identifiers.
Language	The primary language of the resource.
Link to publication	Include the web addresses or DOIs for any publication, important internal reports or other datasets that are related to your dataset.
Keywords	Keywords that associate with the data resource.

As this table shows, each data resource will have a unique identifier, e.g. a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). As we are committed to sharing all our open data on Zenodo a DOI will be generated automatically and this will serve as our main data identifier.

2.2. MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

General rules regarding accessibility

Critical Making partners support the request to open up the outcomes of research results. The Critical Making members are going to use Open Source licenses for software and non-exclusive licences for other Intellectual

Properties such as patents or standardisation proposals. Also, access to the collected data will be open and free. Peer-reviewed scientific publications that result from the project will be provided via open access (“gold” model). We will also consider submitting our publications to Open Research Europe (<https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>), the open access publishing platform for scientific articles launched by the European Commission as a free service for H2020 beneficiaries.

Issues related to protecting intellectual property are highly important when citizens and volunteers are involved in the work. The **Consortium Agreement (CA)** (signed by all partners before project start) is the place where the details of Intellectual Property Rights, including open licenses, between partners are defined, taking care that the rights of citizens and volunteers are equally considered. The CA also includes a list of pre-existing know-how (according to the description of work) and knowledge as well as the major principles on exploitation and dissemination issues. The partners have already agreed that access rights on the pre-existing know-how needed for carrying out the project shall be granted on a royalty-free basis.

Research data access

The main part of raw and processed data generated by the project will be accessible to all consortium partners, unless there is sensitive data that requires data being kept only by the partner having collected the data. As described in the Project Handbook, the main workflow for data sharing starts at the WP level, where each team is responsible for respecting ethical procedures at all times during the data gathering and processing steps. The WP/working team members are also responsible for any data anonymisation or pseudonymization, if applicable. The data accessible to the whole consortium will be stored on the shared Nextcloud server provided by ZSI. Only members of the consortium, after validation from the coordinator (Barbara Kieslinger), can access this space. The public data will be accessible by Zenodo.

Confidential data and data collected for internal purposes will be stored in the secure facilities of the organization responsible for collecting the data and will be retained for two years after the end of project. The data containing personal identifiable information of individuals will only be shared based on a confidentiality agreement (see Annex I of the Project Handbook). A data exchange form, signed by the partners exchanging sensitive data, documents the data exchange between these partners. This form is also provided in the Project Handbook.

Details concerning the ownership, transfer and dissemination of project results are defined in section 8 of the Consortium Agreement and shall be followed accordingly. The relevant rules of the Grant Agreement, in specific Article 26(2), Article 29(1) and Article 30, are also relevant and apply accordingly.

Sensitive Social Science Data

In Critical Making we are dealing with a lot of qualitative (social science) data (see Table 2 below), which is often context sensitive data and includes personal data. GDPR applies for any such personal data.

‘personal data’ means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person; (Art. 4 (1)GDPR)

Thus, we have to pay special attention to direct but also even more so to indirect identifiers in our data, which could make persons identifiable through aggregation of information. For special categories of personal data it may even be necessary to provide for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the fundamental rights and the interests of the data subject. Protection of data subjects according to GDPR rules is clearly prevailing over

our commitment and intention to contribute as much as possible to open research.

There are certain measures that can be taken to make qualitative social scientific data still available and shareable, and we will make use of these measures as far as possible. This includes e.g. clear procedures for **informed consent** (see our project handbook for details), **anonymisation**, **pseudonymisation** of personal data or **access restrictions**.

For pseudonymisation we suggest removing direct and indirect identifiers by:

- Deleting the information
- Substituting the information with a pseudonym (more relevant for qualitative data, e.g. interview transcripts)
- Aggregating the information (more relevant for quantitative data, e.g. numeric data set)

The AUSSDA - The Austrian Social Science Data Archive is offering support for data pseudonymisation via pseudonymisation checks. As the ZSI is a collaboration partner of AUSSDA we can make use of this service for our Critical Making research data. Still, if we anonymise or pseudonymise the data to make it shareable we have to ask ourselves the question of how far the sharing of this qualitative and often highly context sensitive data makes sense and how far this data could then still be reused by others.

If we allow restricted access to the research data to enable data sharing for scientific purposes, we will follow the principle “as open as possible - as closed as necessary”. Such restricted access could be granted to a predefined group of users or to certain accounts and under certain conditions. Within the consortium we also have a data sharing agreement in order to exchange research data within the consortium. Such restricted access could be granted in accordance with the research subjects to consortium-external researchers.

As mentioned above, in cases where data sets can be made freely available as they do not include any personalised data we will make them available with the corresponding metadata on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>).

2.3. MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

The interoperability of the data mostly depends on the metadata that is provided with the data. Table 1 above described the general metadata that we provide with any of our data sets. In addition, Zenodo requires metadata for the description of any data shared on the portal. This metadata uses a vocabulary that is following the FAIR data principles and that offers export options to international standard formats, such as Dublin Core, to make the data interoperable.

To allow inter-disciplinary interoperability we plan to be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data sets. However, there may be uncommon vocabularies being used that stem from the maker-specific context in which we are operating. These context specific vocabularies may need some additional explanation to be provided with the data in order to make them interoperable across disciplines.

2.4. INCREASE DATA RE-USE (THROUGH CLARIFYING LICENCES)

The main users of data produced in the project are the consortium partners. Following an open and participatory approach towards data sharing and re-use, we also consider our participants in our research actions as potential users of the collected data. As all data may be classified into open, sensitive and closed data, the access and re-usability depends on the classification of the data. For re-use of the data the following applies:

- Open data must be acknowledged by citing the data set. Permission from the main data creator (main researcher) or contributors is not required.
- Sensitive (or confidential/restricted data) may be made available by the data creator after any identifying information has been removed. For the reuse of this anonymised/pseudonymised data re-use may be possible, if cited and agreed with the data creator and contributors.
- Closed data are not available for sharing or re-use.

The open data generated in this project will have the CC-BY license to permit its re-use. As previously mentioned, all relevant data will be preserved and archived in Zenodo. As far as we can say this today, all data and items on Zenodo will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. There is currently no intention to remove the shared data from the repository at a given time. Zenodo is hosted by CERN which has an experimental programme defined for the next 20+ years, offering a long-time accessibility of the data.

3. Allocation of resources

Critical Making is part of the H2020 Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP), a pilot action on open access to research data, which requires projects to define and execute a data management plan. Open Data Management is part of Task T1.5 of the Management Workpackage, under the lead of the coordinator ZSI. All other consortium partners are committed to contribute to the data management in their roles as Workpackage leaders. The workflow of how data will be published is depicted in Fig 1 below (as outlined in the handbook).

Figure 1: Open Access workflow

As outlined in the Project Handbook, the Data Management Plan may have to be revised during the course of project activities. As the co-design approach is a rather dynamic methodology it is not possible to clearly specify all data sources and collected outcomes from the beginning.

The costs for making any of our research data FAIR can be covered by the project budget during the official funding period. According to the Grant Agreement, costs related to open access to research data are eligible as part of the Horizon 2020 grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).

4. Data security

All research data from this project is either stored on the collaboration space Nextcloud, which is running on a ZSI server and fully GDPR compliant. ZSI is running its own IT infrastructure; IT staff cares about data security and protection and is taking these measures, among others:

- in-house servers controlled exclusively by ZSI IT staff
- services running in a demilitarized network zone behind a redundant firewall
- resource isolation for services through hardware nodes and/or virtual machines
- regular updates of system and application software
- timely installation of security patches from OSS suppliers
- daily backups, off-site backup on encrypted hard disks, monitoring and logging
- web server hardening
- password policy
- consulting and awareness raising of ZSI staff in data protection issues
- precautions for emergency scenarios
- compliance with GDPR

The Nextcloud collaboration space has a versioning service so data can also be restored in case of any accidental deletion. Consortium partners may also store the data they generated on their own secure servers, making sure that secure storage is guaranteed. The conditions for transfer of any sensitive data is already described above and in the Project Handbook.

Under no circumstance will Critical Making include, store or process private information, pictures etc. without the explicit and written permission of the respective persons. Critical Making will comply fully with data protection issues as laid down in the currently applicable Data Protection Directive EC 95/46, the General Data Protection Regulation EU/2016/679 and the e-Privacy Directive EC 2002/58 (confidentiality of information, treatment of traffic data, spam, and cookies) when collecting mailing lists of operational personnel and under no circumstance will share this information with 3rd parties.

5. Ethical aspects

Research must respect ethical standards and fundamental rights to respond to societal challenges.

During the lifetime of the project, Critical Making will continuously follow up an approach that ensures an appropriate level of ethical sensitivity, meaning that any changes and implementations will be viewed from an ethical perspective and (if needed) actions taken accordingly. The research partner organisations have internal ethical boards and will seek their approval for any data sensitive activities.

The Project Handbook describes the ethical standards we apply for our research in detail, which are aligned with our principles of responsible research.

Gender equality and gender diversity

The Critical Making project fully supports the European Union policy on equal opportunities between women and men as well as gender diverse persons. To this end, participation of all genders is continually encouraged and supported. Project staff of all partners is composed according to the principle of equal opportunity and all member organisations strongly enforce an equal opportunity policy in their human resources selection processes. In addition, in our research we are aware of inherent gender biases and will follow a

gender-sensitive methodology, following gender-sensitive principles. Any dataset openly shared will be controlled for bias, as well as research ethics and integrity. In addition, WP3 is specifically dedicated to gender aspects.

Enhancement of current education processes to better equip future researchers and society as a whole with the necessary competences to participate in research processes.

Of specific importance for Critical Making is the aspect of learning and knowledge sharing, within the specific case actions as well as beyond. Transferring our findings into useful knowledge resources, e.g. open educational resources stemming from WP5 and WP6, for science as well as for the affected communities and future policies is critical. Thus, specific activities in WP3 and WP4 are dedicated to co-designing and testing measures to support competence building, especially skills that are highly relevant for the future such as critical thinking, sustainable making and digital fabrication skills.

6. Summary and outlook

This document, together with the Project Handbook (D1.1), describes the main aspects of how this project is practicing open research and how we are handling our research data. While showing full commitment to Open Science and Openness as default, the privacy and data security of personal data coming from our research participants is of highest priority. Basic templates and procedures, also for ethical compliance, are in place and will be reflected in the consortium.

As research data management is a continuous process and we can currently not foresee all eventualities that may come up by following an open co-design methodology we will reflect and update this DMP in the course of the project.

7. References

Di Rosa, Matteo, Iasillo, Claudia, & Jurkiewicz, Karolina. (2021). D7.4 First version of the Data Management Plan (Version 1). Zenodo. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4726898 last accessed on 31.05.2021 from: <https://zenodo.org/record/4726899#.YK9zv5MzZTb>

European Commission. (2016) H2020 templates: Data management plan v1.0 – 13.10.2016 last accessed on 14.06.2021 from: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/data-management_en.htm

Heider, Veronika, Raffetseder, Lena, Sanchez Solis, Barbara, & Ulrich, Xenia. (2018). DMP Template for the Social Sciences (Version 1.0). Zenodo. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.1291816 last accessed on 31.05.2021 from: <https://zenodo.org/record/1291816#.YLSVspMzbOQ>

Table2: Data description

Workpackage & activity of data collection	Short data description & aim of the data	Type of data* (observational data, experimental data, ...)	Format of data+ (DOCX, ODF, ODT, PDF, CVS, JPEG, ...)	Reuse of any existing data
WP2: workshop documentations	Feedback and participant input documented during co-ideation workshops	Event-related	extracts from Miro Board and other collaboration tools (PDF, JPEG)	The documentation of the co-ideation workshop is original data collected by the project which was used for D2.1 and might be used for future project activities.
WP2: methodological toolbox for case actions	methodological toolbox: tested, iteratively improved and reviewed together with practitioners. Feedback is gathered and used for the improvement of tools	Derived or Compiled	PDF DOCX XLS audio recordings (MP3) HTML or other web coding language	GIM and RRI frameworks combined and resulting in a questionnaire "Sustainable Making Principles" are further developed into an interactive tool Participatory methods collected are applied in the cases

WP3_ qualitative interviews for case studies in Deliverable D3.1	the interviews are an important element in the case studies as they give first hand insights about the case and offer an exchange format (bi-directional communication) for the stakeholders of the specific cases	Observational data	DOC/DOCX PDF audio files (which format?)	The case studies are backed with existing data published on websites, etc. The interviews are the original data collected by the project.
WP3_co-design documentation	Feedback documented directly during co-design sessions regarding the co-design process itself	Event-related	extracts from Miro Board and other collaboration tools (PDF, JPEG)	some data from the WP3 qualitative interviews may be re-used for the co-design of gender-specific interventions
WP3_Online Role Models documentation	Collection of online representation of gender inclusive role models (the data includes links to YouTube videos, comments, etc.)	Derived or Compiled	XLS/XLSX	Based on existing data from YouTube and other online channels
WP3_Analysis of Wikifactory database	Collection of anonymised/unidentifiable datasets to analyse gender responsiveness in the	Derived or Compiled	XLS/XLSX	Based on existing data from Wikifactory.

	<p>database. Manual data sourcing through the quadrat method for sampling. Filtering by demographic factors with the aim to qualitatively study content and language variations within categories. Datasets are based on public projects and stories.</p>			
<p>WP3_interviews of participants of gender-related activities</p>	<p>during the implementation of the co-designed interventions participants will be interviewed to give insights into how they perceive these interventions</p>	<p>Observational</p>	<p>DOC/DOCX PDF audio/video files (M4A & MP4)</p>	
<p>WP4_Review of existing initiatives, projects and practices to integrate young people in (critical)</p>	<p>Compilation of existing initiatives, projects and practices – ranging from FabLabs and makerspaces, educational programmes, schools with making activities, events, research</p>	<p>Derived or Compiled, Reference or Canonical</p>	<p>DOC/DOCX/ODT PDF JPEG</p>	<p>Reuse of previous collections of Making Education activities</p>

making activities for Deliverable 4.1	projects, online platforms, publications, funding opportunities or competitions.			
WP4_Interviews with participants at Youth Makeathon, Critical Making festival and meet ups	Collection of data to inform co-created measures to engage youth in Critical Making. Measures are developed through input directly from participants at the Festival, Makeathons and Meet Ups from surveys and /or interviews (the collection of data from minors, including images, video, or other documentation, will be subject to the informed consent procedure described in D1.1 "Project Handbook".)	Observational, Event-related, Derived or Compiled	DOC/DOCX/ODT PDF JPEG Audio files [mp3 / mp4]	No reuse of pre-existing data Use of data compiled by the project

<p>WP4_Events documentations</p>	<p>Feedback and participant input documented (the collection of data from minors, including images, video, or other documentation, will be subject to the informed consent procedure described in D1.1 "Project Handbook".)</p>	<p>Event-related</p>	<p>DOC/DOCX/ODT PDF JPEG Videos (MPEG-4)</p>	<p>The documentation of the events (Critical Making festival, Makeathon, Meet Ups) is original data collected by the project and might be used for future project activities.</p>
<p>WP4_Expert interviews</p>	<p>Interviews with experts from the fields of education, making education and critical making to discuss findings from Task 4.2</p>	<p>Observational</p>	<p>DOC/DOCX/ODT Audio files (mp4)</p>	<p>The interviews are the original data collected by the project. Some links to resources and further information can be supplied by the interview partners.</p>
<p>WP5_Collection of existing initiatives, tools and practices for openness in (critical) making for Deliverable 5.1 and website</p>	<p>Compilation of existing initiatives, tools and practices – ranging from current activities, tools and toolkits, incubators and accelerators, open hardware business models, standards and licensing, to templates for</p>	<p>Derived or Compiled, Reference or Canonical</p>	<p>XLS/XLSX PDF Videos (YouTube) HTML or other web coding language</p>	<p>Existing data from online sources were researched and collected.</p>

	documentation, reproducibility and distributed manufacturing.			
WP5_Exploratory expert interviews for Deliverable D5.1	Exploratory interviews with 5 makers from 4 countries who are experts on openness in making and provided new insights as well as evaluations of resources collected for D5.1	Observational	DOCX HTML or other web coding language	The interviews are the original data collected by the project. Some links to resources and further information were supplied by the interview partners.
WP5_Documentation of Co-Design Workshop during Critical Making kick-off event	Input and feedback documented directly during the workshop	Event-related	Extracts from Miro Board and other collaboration tools (PDF, JPEG)	The documentation of the co-design workshop is original data collected by the project which was used for D5.1 and might be used for future project activities.
WP5_Survey	Survey shared via different maker networks to evaluate what kind of meanings makers give for openness and social responsibility in their activities	Derived or compiled	XLS/XLSX/ODS HTML or other web coding language	The survey will be conducted online as part of T5.1. The data will be exported into XLSX file format for anonymized usage in D5.4,

				and potentially also inform D5.2 and D5.2.
WP5_Applications for Critical Making Open Hardware Mentoring Program	Data collected from applicants, including organizational and contact data, as well as information about their proposed projects	Derived or Compiled	XLS/XLSX/ODS HTML or other web coding language	The applications will be handed in through the project website and used to execute T5.3. The data will be exported into XLSX file format for anonymized usage in D5.2, and potentially also inform D5.3 and D5.4.
WP5_Interviews with participants at the beginning and end of the Critical Making Open Hardware Mentoring Program	We will conduct thematic entry and exit interviews with the participants of the program to evaluate their perceptions on how they fill the term openness with meaning, which interrelations between open hardware business models and social responsibility they are guided by, and how they	Observational	DOC/DOCX/ODT XLS/XLSX/ODS Audio files (mp4)	The interviews are part of T5.3. The data will be used on the project website, as well as in D5.2, and potentially also in D5.3 and D5.4.

	embrace critical thinking in their making practices, as well as possible changes of perceptions during the course of the program.			
WP5_Documentation of Critical Making Open Hardware Mentoring Program	The program embraces reflexivity and co-creation, the documentations will therefore be crucial for our own reflexivity as part of our responsible research for the T5.4 study.	Observational	DOC/DOCX/ODT XLS/XLSX/ODS Audio files (mp4) HTML or other web coding language Extracts from Miro Board and other collaboration tools (PDF, JPEG)	Based on the T5.4 study, we will compile a summary of guidelines on how to promote social responsibility as part of open hardware development in D5.3. The results will also feed into WP6 and the co-designed methodological toolbox of WP2
WP6_Background expert interviews to collect input for the Critical Making evaluation framework	Interviews of selected RRI experts to get input for the Critical Making RRI & SDG evaluation framework.	Observational	DOC/ Audio files	The data will be used by the project members to create the evaluation framework and the Critical Making Responsibility framework. Not shared.

WP6_interim and final evaluation data: surveys	Survey data (specific type of collected material for will be decided as part of evaluation framework design) to be collected for RRI evaluation in different case actions	Observational	XLS/ HTML, or other Web coding language	The data will be used internally for the project evaluation
WP6_interim and final evaluation data, qualitative interviews	Thematic evaluation interviews of project members & selected case action participants.	Observational	DOC/ Audio files	The data will be used internally for the project evaluation
WP6_Evaluation workshop data	Project team and selected case participants are invited to give their feedback on the RRI and SDG impacts of project action in a collaborative evaluation workshop.	Event-related	extracts from Miro Board and other collaboration tools (PDF, JPEG), audio recordings	The data will be used internally for the project evaluation and to elaborate the final Critical Making Responsibility Framework and guidelines.
WP7_Statistical data about communication and dissemination activities	Statistical data about communication and dissemination activities will be generated by the main communication channels, i.e.	Observational data Derived/compiled	DOC/DOCX XLS/XLSX HTML or other web coding language	No reuse of pre-existing data. The documentation of the events original data collected by the project and might be used for future project activities.

	website and social media accounts.			
WP7_Events related data	Data collected during communication and outreach events such as: list of participants and presentations, videos and photos (their collection will be subject to the informed consent procedure described in the "Project Handbook" deliverable 1.1).	Event-related	DOC/DOCX XLS/XLSX PDF Photo format (JPEG, PNG) Video Format (e.g., .MKV, .MP4, .AVI)	The data might possibly be re-used for follow-up projects from the consortium partners (this use of data is likewise subject to the informed consent procedure described in the project handbook deliverable 1.1).

* Observational, Experimental, Simulation, Derived/complied, Reference/canonical, Event-related

*e.g. XML, .DOC /.DOCX, ODF, ODT, .XLS / .XLSX, .PPT / .PPTX, .CSV, .PDF, Photo Format (e.g., JPEG, .PNG), Video Format (e.g., .MKV, .MP4, .AVI)